

iron, manganese and vanadium are metals with similar properties. In this case, calculation of the thermophysical properties of alloys can be carried out according to the additivity rule.

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Differential assimilation coefficients in computer steelmaking and out-of-furnace processing control systems

The paper outlines theoretical and practical principles of constructing a computer control system for smelting and out-of-furnace steel processing using differential assimilation coefficients (DAC). A detailed derivation of the DAC is given in explicit form for the metal-slag system and the final formulas for the metal-slag-gas system are given. The requirements that the DAC matrix must satisfy are listed. The fundamental possibility of effectively checking the original thermodynamic model using DAC is shown. A calculation scheme for using DAC for optimal design and control of melting and out-of-furnace processing of steel in a wide range of input and output parameters is presented.

steelmaking, assimilation coefficients, computer system, thermodynamic model, charge materials, metal-slag-gas system, simplex method, optimal projecting.

Assimilation coefficients have long been used in metallurgical production in determining the quantities of charge materials necessary to obtain the required composition of the intermediate or finished metal. The values used are based on the average statistical data characteristic for a given smelting period, the composition of the initial metal, target steel grade, and availability of charge materials. Any deviation of these parameters in either direction with a high probability leads to emergency situations and, as a consequence, to production defects. The reason for this is that in reality the assimilation coefficients are not constants, but depend on the temperature, composition of the metal, slag and gas phases, as well as on the composition of used charge materials. Moreover, assimilation of some elements may decrease or increase with the addition of other chemical elements. That is, there are cross effects whose influence is known only at the empirical level for a few cases.

The limit of possibilities provided by the knowledge of average statistical assimilation coefficients was reached in the “Forward” information technology system [1], in which the optimal quantities of charge materials were calculated without taking into account the complex physicochemical processes occurring in the steelmaking unit (or ladle). In particular, one of its significant drawbacks was the impossibility to optimize the quantities of non-metallic charge materials, which did not make it possible to design technologies for desulfurization, dephosphorization, direct alloying, etc. In another “Oracul” system [2], these restrictions were partially lifted, but remained serious problems with the adequacy and sustainability of the results.

The principal role of the supplier of complete information about the «metal-slag-gas» system is assigned to a deterministic thermodynamic model that can take into account the mutual influence of elements and adequately represent the equilibrium state in the form of a system of equations in a general form:

$$F_i(m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k; \bar{m}_{[1]}, \bar{m}_{[2]}, \dots, \bar{m}_{[k]}, p, T) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k – masses of elements in a system; $\bar{m}_{[1]}, \bar{m}_{[2]}, \dots, \bar{m}_{[k]}$ – equilibrium masses of elements in metal; p – pressure, and T – absolute temperature.

In other words, if the masses of elements are given, then such a model “should” distribute them between metal, slag, and gas. Using implicit differentiation of the system of equations (1) one can determine values $U_{ij} = \partial m_{[i]} / \partial m_j$:

$$U_{ij} = \frac{\partial m_{[i]}}{\partial m_j} = - \left[\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial m_{[j]}} \right]^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial m_j} \right] \Bigg|_{m_{[i]} = \bar{m}_{[i]}}, \quad (2)$$

which make up the square matrix and are the sought **differential assimilation coefficients** (DAC). The physical meaning of the DAC values is quite simple: “how much will the mass of element i in the *metal* change when adding a unit mass of element j to the whole *system*”. Thus, it becomes possible to take into account all the cross effects of the influence of some elements on the content of others.

At the same time, the general formula (2) does not give an idea of the structure of DAC and is quite problematic in terms of the volume and stability of calculations with a large number of elements taken into account. It seems appropriate, using the formalism of the thermodynamic model, to bring the DAC to a compact form, convenient for both calculations and analysis of their structure.

Derivation of differential assimilation coefficients in explicit form

As the basic thermodynamic model of the “metal-slag-gas” system (1), a deterministic physico-chemical model is used that most accurately describes the processes occurring in the steelmaking unit on the basis of Gibbs chemical potentials method [3-6]. An essential characteristic feature of this model is the inclusion of the electronic contribution to the chemical potential of elements in the slag. It will be shown below that the adequacy of this model can be tested using the obtained expressions for DACs, *regardless* of the accepted models of metal and slag solutions.

Let us first derive the DAC for the “metal-slag” system. The initial system of $k + 1$ non-linear equations based on the equality of the chemical potentials of elements in the metal and slag, in this case, has the form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{x_{(i)}}{x_{[i]}} = \frac{K_{[i]} \gamma_i}{\psi_i} \exp\left(-\frac{\mu \nu_i}{RT}\right), \quad i = 1..k; \\ \sum_{i=1}^k x_{(i)} \nu_i = 0, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $x_{(i)}$ – molar fractions of elements in slag; $x_{[i]}$ – molar fractions of elements in metal; $K_{[i]}$ – metal-slag equilibrium constants; γ_i – coefficients of activity of elements in metal; ψ_i – coefficients of activity of elements in slag; ν_i – valencies of elements in slag; μ – redox potential of the system (Fermi level of electrons in slag); T – system temperature; R – universal gas constant.

We perform the following sequence of transformations on the system of equations (3):

1. Pass from molar fractions to the moles of elements in the metal $n_{[i]} = N_m x_{[i]}$ and slag $n_{(i)} = N_s x_{(i)}$, respectively, where N_m and N_s are the total number of moles in the metal and slag. In this case, the sum of the moles of each element in the metal and slag is equal to the number of moles of this element in the system $n_i = n_{[i]} + n_{(i)}$;
2. Introduce expression $A_i = \ln(K_{[i]}\gamma_i / \psi_i)$ and name the quantities A_i as the natural logarithms of the consolidated (or effective) metal-slag equilibrium constants;
3. Redox potential of the system μ will be further measured in units of RT . So the denominator RT disappears.
4. Introduce the variable $Y = \ln(N_m / N_s)$, which is equal to the natural logarithm of the reciprocal of the molar multiplicity of slag.

After the substitution $n_{[i]} = n_i - n_{(i)}$, the transformed system of equations takes the following form:

$$\begin{cases} n_{(i)} = \frac{n_i}{1 + \exp(-A_i + Y + \mu\nu_i)}, & i = 1..k; \\ \sum_{i=1}^k n_{(i)}\nu_i = 0. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In the obtained equations, the number of moles of an element in slag $n_{(i)}$ is expressed in terms of the number of moles of this element in the system n_i and the variables μ and Y . The next step is to eliminate the variables $n_{(i)}$ using the fact that the sum of moles in slag can be represented in two ways :

1. As the sum of values $n_{(i)}$;
2. As a fraction of the total number of moles in the system N , expressed through the variable Y .

Equating the obtained expressions for the sum of moles in the slag, we arrive at a compact system of two nonlinear equations for the unknown variables μ and Y , which is completely equivalent to the original system (3):

$$\begin{cases} F_1 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i\nu_i}{1 + \exp(-A_i + Y + \mu\nu_i)} = 0; \\ F_2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{1 + \exp(-A_i + Y + \mu\nu_i)} - \frac{N}{1 + \exp(Y)} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The advantages of system (5) are that its solution by numerical methods is stable, and the required accuracy is achieved approximately k times faster than when solving the original system of $k + 1$ non-linear equations. In addition, the compact Jacobi matrices of system (5) make it possible to obtain DAC in explicit form.

Values of μ and Y have been the solution to system (5). With those values, after substitution (4), we obtain the equilibrium molar composition of the slag $\bar{n}_{(1)}, \bar{n}_{(2)}, \dots, \bar{n}_{(k)}$ and the equilibrium molar composition of the metal $\bar{n}_{[1]}, \bar{n}_{[2]}, \dots, \bar{n}_{[k]}$. It is important to note that after solving this system, the number of moles of elements in the metal $n_{[i]}$ and slag $n_{(i)}$, as well as their sums N_m and N_s in all subsequent expressions become equilibrium values. For readability, we omit the line above them.

Using equations (4), we represent the number of moles of element i in the metal in the form:

$$n_{[i]} = n_i - n_{(i)} = \frac{n_i}{1 + \exp(A_i - Y - \mu\nu_i)}. \quad (6)$$

First we find the general form of the matrix of molar DACs. To do this, we use the differentiation rule for the complex function (6) $n_{[i]} = f_i(n_i, \mu, Y)$:

$$V_{ij} = \frac{\partial n_{[i]}}{\partial n_j} = \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial n_i} \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial n_j} + \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial \mu} \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j} + \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial Y} \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j}; \quad (7)$$

Partial derivatives $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial n_i}$, $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial \mu}$, $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial Y}$ are found directly from (6) by differentiation with respect

to the corresponding variables. The derivative $\frac{\partial n_i}{\partial n_j}$ is equal to the Kronecker symbol δ_{ij} . As a result, after substituting from (4) and (6), we obtain the structural formula for the molar DAC:

$$V_{ij} = \frac{n_{[i]}}{n_i} \left(\delta_{ij} + v_i n_{(i)} \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j} + n_{(i)} \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j} \right). \quad (8)$$

Remaining derivatives are found by implicit differentiation of the system of equations (5):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j} \\ \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j} \end{bmatrix} = -\mathbf{J}_1^{-1} \mathbf{J}_2 = - \left[\frac{\partial(F_1, F_2)}{\partial(\mu, Y)} \right]^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial(F_1, F_2)}{\partial n_j} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j} = -\frac{1}{D} \left[\frac{n_{(j)} v_j}{n_j} \left(\frac{N_s N_m}{N} - \sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]}}{n_h} \right) + \left(\frac{n_{(j)}}{n_j} - \frac{N_s}{N} \right) \sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]} v_h}{n_h} \right]; \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j} = -\frac{1}{D} \left[\frac{n_{(j)} v_j}{n_j} \sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]} v_h}{n_h} - \left(\frac{n_{(j)}}{n_j} - \frac{N_s}{N} \right) \sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]} v_h^2}{n_h} \right], \quad (11)$$

where D is the Jacobian of system (5):

$$D = - \left(\sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]} v_h}{n_h} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{N_s N_m}{N} - \sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]}}{n_h} \right) \sum_{h=1}^k \frac{n_{(h)} n_{[h]} v_h^2}{n_h}. \quad (12)$$

The most important feature of the obtained formulae for DAC is the fact that they do not explicitly contain the equilibrium constants and activity coefficients in the metal and slag. The latter are already taken into account in equilibrium values $n_{[1]}, n_{[2]}, \dots, n_{[k]}$; $n_{(1)}, n_{(2)}, \dots, n_{(k)}$. This means that DAC can be quickly calculated directly from experimental data on the equilibrium composition of the metal and slag, regardless of the adopted solution models in the corresponding phases, for example, according to the express chemical analysis of the selected samples.

On the other hand, these same formulae allow an effective experimental verification of the adequacy of the initial thermodynamic model by comparing the actual $\Delta \mathbf{n}_\square$ and calculated $\mathbf{V} \Delta \mathbf{n}$ changes in the content of elements in the metal in equilibrium metal-slag systems with similar elemental compositions.

It should be noted that DAC matrix \mathbf{V} cannot be arbitrary. It must satisfy the following obvious conditions:

1. The equilibrium metal added to the system should completely go into the metal:

$$\mathbf{V} \mathbf{n}_\square = \mathbf{n}_\square. \quad (13)$$

2. Similarly, the equilibrium slag added to the system must completely go into the slag, i.e., it should not enter the metal:

$$\mathbf{V} \mathbf{n}_0 = \mathbf{0}. \quad (14)$$

3. When a small amount of arbitrary material is added to the system, part of it moving to the slag should be electrically neutral. In the metal-slag system, this requirement is reduced to the following expression:

$$\mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}. \quad (15)$$

The above formulae for DAC completely satisfy all three conditions.

It must be also noted that the DAC matrix elements are transformed as a second rank tensor during the transition from the elemental composition to the phase composition of the system. Matrix \mathbf{V} becomes diagonal, and its elements are equal to the assimilation coefficients in corresponding phases (1 for metal, and 0 for slag). If the thermodynamic system consists of more than two chemical elements, then virtual zero mass λ -phases with alternating composition are formed in the system besides of metal and slag. However their discussion is beyond the scope of this article.

Differential assimilation coefficients in the “metal-slag-gas” system

For the “metal-slag-gas” system, we supplement the initial system of equations (3) with equations expressing the equality of the chemical potentials of elements in metal and gas:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{x_{(i)}}{x_{[i]}} = \frac{K_{[i]}\gamma_i}{\psi_i} \exp\left(-\frac{\mu v_i}{RT}\right), \quad i = 1..k; \\ \frac{x_{(i)}}{x_{[i]}} = \frac{K_{[i]}\gamma_i}{\lambda_i}, \quad i = 1..k; \\ \sum_{i=1}^k x_{(i)}v_i = 0. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

An approach using the elemental composition of the gas $x_{(i)}$, the corresponding “metal-gas” equilibrium constants $K_{[i]}$, and the activity coefficients of the elements in the gas λ_i allows to unify representation of chemical potentials and activities of elements in a gas and gives the possibility of simultaneous calculation of the partial pressures of many molecular and atomic gases that make up the gas phase.

The method for deriving DAC for a three-phase system does not fundamentally differ from the procedure for deriving DAC for the “metal-slag” system described above. Therefore, only the main results necessary for practical calculations will be given below.

Using similar transformations, we reduce the system of $2k+1$ equations (16) to a system of three equations:

$$\begin{cases} F_1 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i v_i}{1 + \exp(-A_i + Y + \mu v_i) [1 + \exp(B_i - Z)]} = 0; \\ F_2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{1 + \exp(-A_i + Y + \mu v_i) [1 + \exp(B_i - Z)]} - \frac{N}{1 + \exp(Y) [1 + \exp(-Z)]} = 0; \\ F_3 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{1 + [1 + \exp(A_i - Y - \mu v_i)] \exp(Z - B_i)} - \frac{N}{1 + \exp(Z) [1 + \exp(-Y)]} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where $B_i = \ln(K_{[i]}\gamma_i / \lambda_i)$ is the natural logarithm of the consolidated (effective) “metal-gas” equilibrium constant; $Z = \ln(N_m / N_g)$ is the natural logarithm of the reciprocal of the molar multiplicity of the gas.

The result of solving system (17) is a set of values μ , Y , Z , which are used to determine the equilibrium contents of elements in all phases.

Structural formula for DAC in the “metal-slag-gas” system has the following form:

$$V_{ij} = \frac{n_{[i]}}{n_i} \left(\delta_{ij} + v_i n_{(i)} \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j} + n_{(i)} \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j} + n_{(i)} \frac{\partial Z}{\partial n_j} \right). \quad (18)$$

Partial derivatives $\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j}, \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j}, \frac{\partial Z}{\partial n_j}$ are calculated by implicit differentiation of the system of equations (17):

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j}, \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j}, \frac{\partial Z}{\partial n_j} \right] = -\mathbf{J}_1^{-1} \mathbf{J}_2 = - \left[\frac{\partial(F_1, F_2, F_3)}{\partial(\mu, Y, Z)} \right]^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial(F_1, F_2, F_3)}{\partial n_j} \right]. \quad (19)$$

Due to the cumbersomeness of expressions, we do not bring partial derivatives $\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial n_j}, \frac{\partial Y}{\partial n_j}, \frac{\partial Z}{\partial n_j}$ to an explicit form, leaving the readers to do it on their own. For the practical purposes, it suffices to calculate \mathbf{J}_1 and \mathbf{J}_2 , and then use numerical methods of matrix algebra.

Comparing equations (8), (18) and (5), (17) in pairs, one cannot fail to note the strict fulfillment of the *correspondence principle*. That is, in the absence of the gas phase, formulas (17) and (18) for the “metal-slag-gas” system turn into formulas (5) and (8), which are valid for the two-phase “metal-slag” equilibrium.

In subsequent calculations, the matrix of mass DAC \mathbf{U} will be used, the elements of which are calculated from the molar matrix \mathbf{V} according to the formula:

$$U_{ij} = V_{ij} \frac{M_i}{M_j}, \quad (20)$$

where M_i, M_j – atomic masses of elements i and j , respectively.

Application of DAC for optimization of charge materials

DAC are directly used to solve the problem of optimizing the amount of charge materials with guaranteed compliance with the specified composition of the semiproduct or finished metal. In this case, the optimality criterion is the minimum total cost of the selected charge materials. Further, by charge materials (CM) we mean a wide class of materials, including ferroalloys, slag-forming materials, deoxidizers, ligatures, carbon-containing materials, as well as synthetic slags and fluxes, oxygen, inert gases and all types of energy carriers, including hydrogen and electricity.

In order for the semi-finished product or finished metal to satisfy the specified restrictions on the chemical composition, it is necessary that a system of $2k-2$ inequalities be fulfilled (k is the number of elements). In matrix notation, it can be compactly represented as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{U}^L (\mathbf{P}^L + \mathbf{B}^L \mathbf{X})}{\mathbf{I}^T \mathbf{U}^L (\mathbf{P}^L + \mathbf{B}^L \mathbf{X})} \geq \mathbf{F}^L \\ \frac{\mathbf{U}^U (\mathbf{P}^U + \mathbf{B}^U \mathbf{X})}{\mathbf{I}^T \mathbf{U}^U (\mathbf{P}^U + \mathbf{B}^U \mathbf{X})} \leq \mathbf{F}^U \end{cases}, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{U}^L, \mathbf{U}^U$ – matrices of mass differential assimilation coefficients (lower and upper limits); $\mathbf{P}^L, \mathbf{P}^U$ – vectors of the actual initial elemental mass composition of the corresponding systems before charging CM (lower and upper limits), tons; $\mathbf{B}^L, \mathbf{B}^U$ – matrices of the elemental composition of all available CM (lower and upper limits), mass fractions; \mathbf{X} – sought-for vector of optimal CM masses, tons; $\mathbf{F}^L, \mathbf{F}^U$ – vectors of the metal composition regulated by standard (finished metal) or technological instruction (semi-finished product), mass fractions; \mathbf{I}^T – unit vector.

The matrices $\mathbf{U}^L, \mathbf{U}^U$ are obtained from (18-20) by thermodynamic calculation of equilibrium in the “metal-slag-gas” systems with current compositions $\mathbf{P}^L + \mathbf{B}^L \mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{P}^U + \mathbf{B}^U \mathbf{X}$, respectively.

Vectors $\mathbf{B}^L \mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{B}^U \mathbf{X}$ have the meaning of added chemical elements to the system with charge materials \mathbf{X} .

Using elementary transformations, we reduce the system of inequalities (21) to the form $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} \leq \mathbf{H}_0$, suitable for its solution by the simplex method:

$$\begin{cases} (\mathbf{F}^L \mathbf{I}^T - \mathbf{E}) \mathbf{U}^L \mathbf{B}^L \mathbf{X} \leq (\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{F}^L \mathbf{I}^T) \mathbf{U}^L \mathbf{P}^L \\ (\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{F}^U \mathbf{I}^T) \mathbf{U}^U \mathbf{B}^U \mathbf{X} \leq (\mathbf{F}^U \mathbf{I}^T - \mathbf{E}) \mathbf{U}^U \mathbf{P}^U \end{cases}, \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{E} is a unit matrix.

In the matrices \mathbf{B}^L and \mathbf{B}^U , the lower and upper compositions of materials are taken, respectively, for all elements, excluding the solvent (as a rule, iron), the mass fraction of which is calculated as a complement to unity. Two inequalities corresponding to the solvent are excluded from system (22).

We supplement obtained inequalities with a system of inequalities of the form $\mathbf{R}\mathbf{X} \leq \mathbf{R}_0$, taking into account all kinds of technological and organizational constraints, such as:

- required and permissible mass of semi-finished or finished metal;
- actual quantities of CM available in the workshop (in the warehouse);
- constraints on the group and proportion of individual CM, presence of mandatory CM;
- maximum permissible decrease (increase) in the metal temperature when charging CM;
- marginal parameters of the dispensers used (tuyeres, burners, electric controllers);
- ultimate parameters of the metallurgical unit, including its minimum and maximum performance, load, permissible temperature of the working volume;
- temporal constraints;

The complete system of inequalities with respect to the sought-for vector of charge materials \mathbf{X} will look like:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H} \\ \mathbf{R} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{X} \leq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_0 \\ \mathbf{R}_0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

Obtained system of inequalities is solved iteratively by the dual simplex method using a fast computation algorithm. In this case, the functional of the total cost of CM, equal to $\mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{X}$, where \mathbf{Q} is the price vector, is minimized. Iterations stop when the modulus of the vector $\Delta \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_0$ is less than some small specified value.

Thus, presented theoretical approach and calculation scheme make it possible to effectively solve problems of steelmaking optimal control and design in a practically unlimited range of input and output parameters. Corresponding algorithms for EAF, ladle furnace, and alloying on the drain are implemented in a real time computer system for monitoring and controlling steelmaking process.

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